

CHAPTER ONE

PROFILE OF THE PROBLEM

(1.1): ANALYSIS OF ACCIDENT IN 5 YEARS:

Safety in Indian Railways becomes a subject of discussion when there is an accident. The review of train accidents of the last 5 years (2009-10 to 2013-14) for which the data is available indicates that a large number of accidents happen because of derailments & at level crossing. It is also clear that more than 80% of the accidents are caused by Human Failure (Railway Staff or Otherwise). The good sign however is that the number of accidents per million kilometers run and number of casualties per million passengers carried has come down in the last few years.

Fig. (1.1): Graph of 5 years accident history.

Fig. (1.2): Percentage graph of 5 years accident history.

(1.2): HISTORY OF FIRE ACCIDENTS AFTER INDEPENDENCE OF INDIA:

Although there are 23 accidents in past 5 years but once a time it was very high even more then there is a complete list of Fire accidents in Indian Railways in which casualties were very high.

1. 23 February 1985 – Rajnandgaon train fire, Madhya Pradesh, India: Over 50 people were killed when an express train caught fire. [1]
2. 16 April 1990– Patna rail disaster, near Patna, India: 70 killed as shuttle train is gutted by fire.
3. 6 June 1990: Thirty-five killed in a fire accident in train at Gollaguda in Andhra Pradesh.
4. 10 October 1990: Forty killed in a fire in a train near Cherlapalli in Andhra Pradesh.
5. 26 October 1994: Twenty-seven killed as 8001 DN Mumbai–Howrah Mail caught fire on its S5 Sleeper class coach between Lotapahar and CKP stations (SE Railway) at 02.51 AM.
6. 14 May 1995: Fifty-two people killed as Madras–Kanyakumari Express met with fire accident near Salem.
7. On 15 May 2003, fire breaks out in Golden Temple Mail at 3.55 hrs between Ludhiana and Ladhawal stations, resulting in 36 deaths and 15 injuries.
8. 18 August 2006 two carriages catch fire on the Chennai–Hyderabad Express near Secunderabad station.
9. 13 February 2009 – carriages of the Coromandel Express met with fire accident soon after the train left Jajpur Road station near the city of Jajpur in the state of Orissa.[2]
10. 18 April 2011 – Three coaches of the Mumbai - Delhi Rajdhani Express caught fire near Ratlam district in Madhya Pradesh. The train, carrying nearly 900 passengers caught fire while running between Bikramgarh Alot and Phuria stations in Kota division. The coaches were removed from the train and the fire was put out quickly. No passenger was harmed.[2]
11. 12 July 2011 - New Delhi-Patna Rajdhani Express's coach caught fire near outskirts in New Delhi. No casualties.
12. 22 November 2011 - Howrah-Dehradun express train caught fire- 7 burnt to death. It was around 2.30am when coach number B1 of the Dehradun-bound train caught fire. Later, the fire spread to coach B2. Both coaches were badly burnt, but all the casualties were from B1.[3]
13. 26 February 2012 - Three people died and one man was injured, when Kozhikode-bound Jan Satabdi Express ran into a crowd of people who were watching Uthralikkavu pooram sample fireworks standing on the railway track.[4]
14. 30 July 2012 - One of the coaches of the Chennai-bound Tamil Nadu Express (New Delhi - Chennai) caught fire early on 30 July morning, near Nellore in Andhra Pradesh. 47 people have died and 25 others have been injured.[5]
15. 16 October 2012 - A bogie of the Solapur-bound passenger train from Hyderabad caught fire during its halt at the station in Gulbarga. There were over 15 passengers in the bogie of the Falaknuma Passenger after it arrived at the station at 12:30 PM and caught fire, but six jumped to safety. Some of the passengers were headed for Tuljapur in Maharashtra to

attend the Bhavani festival which takes place during Navaratri. Immolation by couple led to fire in train at Gulbarga station, says Railway police[6]

16. 30 Nov 2012 - At least two AC coaches of GT Express caught fire near Gwalior on Friday, claiming several lives
17. 2 November 2013 - 10 people were ran over by 13352 Alapuzha-Dhanbad express, near Gotlam in Vizianagaram district on Saturday evening at around 6:30PM .It started after passengers of the 57271 Vijayawada-Rayagada passenger pulled the chain at the railway yard at Gotlam railway station when they heard a rumour that a compartment of the train was on fire. They then alighted the train and jumped onto the tracks at around 6.50pm .It was dark and the passengers didn't see the express train coming on the adjacent rack. The express train ran over them, killing 10 people, and injuring at least 20.[7]
18. 28 December 2013 - An AC coach of the 16594 Bangalore City-Hazur Sahib Nanded express caught fire near Kothacheruvu in Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh resulting in the death of at least 26 people and injuring 12 others. The incident took place early in the morning around 3:15 am. 54 passengers are expected to be on board in the B1 compartment of the train which was completely gutted in the fire.

CHAPTER TWO

EXISTING SYSTEMS

There are some existing systems braking system for trains. Some of them are published in international journals and filed for the patent.

(2.1): AVOIDANCE OF FIRE ACCIDENT ON RUNNING TRAIN USING ZIGBEE WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK:

The main objective of this present paper is to safe guard people's life and government property. The paper will focus on the system that will detect and control the fire accidents on running train. In-house parameters such as temperature and humidity in the each coach can be monitored in real time. From the information collected by the sensor system, decisions for fire fighting, alarming, and automatic water sprinkler system can be made more quickly by the relevant system or engine driver. After receiving the signal, the engine driver will stop the train and take necessary action. The system is used for monitoring, automatic fire sprinkling, cautioning and preventing of fire in running trains. The fire may occur in any form of activities such as short circuit in the electrical wires, prohibited activities of carrying diesel, petrol, gas stoves and smoking nearby them will cause fire accidents. To control these we do not have an intensive work force. To overcome this, a system of having automatic sensor monitoring, fire alarm warning and fire extinguishing are based on ZigBee wireless sensor network technology. This system can monitor real-time related parameters such as temperature and humidity in each coach. From the information collected by the system, decisions for firefighting, alarming, and automatic operation of the train braking system can be made more quickly by the system or engine driver. The engine driver will get the warning light and he stops the engine. Further he informs to the immediate concern authority for help.[8]

(2.2): ON LINE DETECTION AND AUTO APPLICATION OF BRAKES TO TRAINS IN CASE OF FIRE ACCIDENTS IN TRAINS

The present invention is aimed at sensing the fire in the moving passenger train and giving a warning to the loco pilot, guards, station masters and applying brakes automatically to the trains. The fire and high temperature detectors will be fixed in each bay of the passenger coaches. The sensors will be detecting the fire/high temperature in the coaches and activate a relay in the breaking system of the train. Immediately the brakes will be got operated automatically in case of fire and train will be stopped. The advantages of the system are:

1. The Sensors will be sensing the fire and high temperature in the train and activating relays which in turn will activate the pneumatic/mechanical/hydraulic/electric break system of the coaches and breaks are applied to the train automatically.
2. The system is based on automatic sensing and activating the pneumatic/mechanical/hydraulic/electric break system so no chance of any human error.
3. The system will save human losses in case of fire accidents in trains [9]

(2.3): PREVENTION OF TRAIN ACCIDENTS USING WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS:

The present work is concentrated on predicting the major cause of railway accidents that is collision on the same track. The primary goal of this anti-collision system is to identify collision points and to report these error cases to main control room, Near by station as well as grid control stations. So that if any collision likely to occurs then this system will help to avoid such conditions by giving an alarm to concern units. The current work proposes the implementation of an efficient Zig-Bee based Train Anti-Collision for railways. A safe distance of 1 Km has been maintained between two trains after applying the emergency brake in case of collision detection.[10]

(2.4) A TRAIN SMOKE AND FIRE ALARM SYSTEM BASED ON A WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK AND A METHOD:

The invention relates to a train smoke and fire alarm system based on a wireless sensor network and a method. The train smoke and fire alarm system based on the wireless sensor network comprises several smoke and fire alarm nodes distributed inside a train body and used for acquiring information of each point, a gateway node used for collecting the information of each smoke and fire alarm node and carrying out classification and arrangement on the information of each smoke and fire alarm node, and a train network control system used for carrying out extraction on alarm and fault information and carrying out alarm prompting. Wireless communication connection is carried out among the smoke and fire alarm nodes and between the smoke and fire alarm nodes and the gateway node. Wired connection exists between the gateway node and the train network control system. Through the wireless transmission mode, wiring in the vehicle body is not needed, so that simplicity and convenience are realized, and burden for the train is reduced. At the same time, real time, intelligent and Omni bearing smoke and fire status monitoring can be carried out on the high speed train. In addition, alarming can be carried out, so that the adoption of corresponding measures for smoke and fire calamities is convenient and hidden smoke and fire risks of the high speed train are eliminated. [11]

(2.5): METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR DETECTING DEFECTS AND HAZARDOUS CONDITIONS IN PASSING RAIL VEHICLES:

This invention concerns the field of rail transportation safety and, particularly, the detection for a consist of at least one passing rail vehicles of at least one defect and/or hazardous condition comprising gauge profile hazards, shifted loads, overheating, failures and incipient failures in axles bearings, overheating of wheels and brakes, overheating of vehicle body parts and fire on board. The invention concerns a Method and a System to perform a series of detection functions for rail vehicles defects and hazardous conditions, using wayside-based sensors and measurement instruments along and around the rails.[12]

(2.6): FIRE ALARM WARNING SYSTEM FOR RAILWAY ELECTRIC TRAINS:

Object of the invention is the creation of a system of fire-alarm warning alarm system for railway trains, providing increased stability and reliability of preserving a healthy state it in real perating conditions, and with different kind of paraph cars and composition under the influence of external electromagnetic interference from electric trains, and to automatically determine the address of damage to the communication line control and monitoring station wagon with controllers and thus reduce labor costs for Troubleshooting. This object is achieved due to the fact that the system fire burglar alarm trains containing connected to the power sources symmetric and working alternately depending on the direction of motion of the remote control (PKU), installed in the first and second head. of the train, providing a survey of car controllers, management and sound and light alarm in case of any event connected two-wire communication line installed in every car controllers, each controller connected to the sensors, controlling fire-alarm condition of the car, each SRB contains the generator of the stepping pulses and the generator stepper pulses of the first direction control and monitoring station sends on the wire first impulse on the car controller first carriage which is stored in a memory of the remote marked on the scoreboard PKU, while the rest of the car controller is disconnected from the communication line, and after the transmission data from the controller of the first car on the first FBS this controller and is automatically disconnected from the communication line, includes contact circuit connected to the line controller to the second carriage, the first PKU includes generator stepper pulses, which sends a second pulse and stores in its memory with the designation on the scoreboard PKU, and further, similar to the step by step alternately turn on all railroad controllers until the end of the composition, the encoded signal from the controller, located in the second head carriage includes a second cycle step-by-step survey first PKU, and at the direction of the movement included the second PKU located in the second head carriage and operating similarly.[13]

(2.7): CENTRAL CENTRALIZED TYPE TRAIN CONTROL SYSTEM BASED ON LONG TERM EVOLUTION (LTE) TECHNOLOGY:

The current train control system, there are many independent subsystems using the car to a wireless communication system, such as signaling subsystem, wireless digital cluster subsystem, passenger information subsystem (PIS), civilian communications subsystem, CCTV subsystem SECURITY and fire subsystems, these systems occupy limited wireless network resources, and therefore, the structure of the sub-species of each individual sub-station radio network resource has the presence of wireless signal interference between the various subsystems, transmission stability of the whole train control system low, the network transfer rate is slow and small bandwidth defects. In addition, in order to achieve wireless transmission functions of the system vehicle ground between the trackside you need to install the appropriate equipment and transport carrier, which resulted in a waste of resources, increased investment cost, and increased maintenance. The utility model discloses a central centralized type train control system based on

a long term evolution (LTE) technology. The central centralized type train control system based on the LTE technology comprises a control center, LTE base stations and a train-mounted terminal antenna unit, wherein the LTE base stations are arranged on all train stations, the train-mounted terminal antenna unit is arranged on a train and connected with a train-mounted device through communication, all the LTE base stations are connected between a leaky coaxial cable and a single mode optical fiber transport network, the leaky coaxial cable is used for forming a wireless transmission channel between the LTE base stations and the train-mounted terminal antenna unit, and the single mode optical fiber transport network is used for forming a wire transmission channel between the LTE base stations and the control center. According to the central centralized type train control system, the LTE technology is used for providing a transmission platform with a super-large bandwidth, a network system for wireless communication is built, unified wireless information transmission carriers can be provided for a signal sub-system, a wireless digital cluster sub-system and a passenger information sub-system, transmission and integration of information services, voice services and image services of the systems are achieved, the network transmission rate and the bandwidth are improved, transmission stability of the whole system is enhanced, and wireless interference among all the systems is avoided.[14]

(2.8): THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AUTOMATIC FIRE RESCUING AND INFORMATION SYSTEM IN A TRAIN USING ZIGBEE AND SENSORS NETWORKS:

The present paper is implementing a ZigBee and sensor based information and rescuing system in a train to alert the authorities about the fire accident occurred. ZigBee and sensor network both are effective low cost monitoring system will also help the railway industry for both signaling and communication purpose. Finally presenting a low power embedded system to overcome the fire accidents occurring in railway industry. In this paper a discussion of proposed safety system for railway, using 16f877a microcontroller of PIC as hardware platform, and combine with ZigBee and wireless sensor network as a communication platform of wireless area network. Which can transmit, receive and display warnings and emergency signal sand for sensing the temperature in trains.[15]

(2.9): WIRELESS DEVICE NETWORKS WITH SMOKE DETECTION CAPABILITIES:

The present invention includes an electronic device which may include a smoke detector. The electronic device may use the smoke detector to monitor for the presence of smoke. In response to detecting smoke with the smoke detector, the electronic device may issue an alert or take other suitable action. The electronic device may transmit alerts to nearby electronic devices and to remote electronic devices such as electronic devices at emergency services facilities. Alerts may contain maps and graphical representations of buildings in which smoke has been detected. Motion detectors and other sensors and circuitry may be used in determining whether electronic

devices are being used by users and may be used in determining where the electronic devices are located. Alerts may contain information on the location of detected smoke and building occupants.

(2.10): PASSENGER TRAIN SAFETY CONTROL AND COMMUNICATION SYSTEM:

This invention relates to wireless communication means for vehicles, preferably, railway transport, more specifically, railway vehicle traffic safety means, and can be used for providing passenger trains with wireless dedicated alarms and internal communication, as well as communication with remote subscribers, preferably, traffic control and security services. This invention is intended for use in suburban and long-distance passenger train safety control and communication systems to arrange communication channels and transmitting alarms and passenger train contingency messages. The device is developed on the basis of DECT technologies, allows providing passenger trains with data communication and telephony devices and can be used in flexible passenger train setup mode comprising a command car and passenger cars. [16]

(2.11): IMAGE PROCESSING ALARM SYSTEM AND METHOD FOR AUTOMATICALLY SENSING UNEXPECTED ACCIDENT RELATED TO TRAIN:

The present invention relates to an image processing alarm system and a method for automatically sensing an unexpected accident related to a train. In the present invention, a platform railway part, a platform boarding part and a train car door part are continuously monitored using a plurality of image sensing apparatuses. In the case that there is not any train car at the platform, a certain image to be used for checking the current situation of the platform is transmitted to a following train, a station office and a central command office based on a wired method or wireless method. When a person is fallen at the platform railway part in the station or a certain emergency situation occurs during an operation of a train, the above state is automatically detected and is alarmed to the following train, the station office, the central command office and various cooperating alarming apparatuses based on an image or audio method. In the case that a certain train is parked at the platform or the train is supposed to just start, a certain image capable of checking a boarding state of a passenger at the platform and a door opening and closing state of a train car during the loading or unloading is transmitted to the train, station office and central command office based on a wired or wireless method. When a certain emergency situation occurs, the emergency situation is automatically detected and is transmitted and alarmed to the train, station office, central command office and various cooperating apparatuses based on an image or audio alarming method, so that a station officer, emergency situation manager and train driver can quickly cope with the emergency situation in the train emergency situation automatic detection image process system and method according to the present invention. Therefore, in the present invention, a corresponding emergency situation measurement is automatically performed with respect to a corresponding emergency level in

such a manner that the emergency is judged with a certain emergency level, and an alarming control signal corresponding to the level is transmitted to the following train, station office, central command office and cooperating alarming apparatuses based on a wired or wireless method for thereby automatically stopping a corresponding train. In addition, various dangerous elements of the surrounding environments such as roads near railway crossings, pedestrian, and various weather conditions are intensively and automatically monitored, so that it is possible to quickly detect various dangerous elements caused by people and train and to take a proper measurement with respect to the elements in the train emergency situation automatic detection image process alarming system and method according to the present invention.[17]

(2.12): AUTOMATIC FIRE INITIATED BRAKING AND ALERT SYSTEM FOR TRAINS:

By every new day alternative technologies are being developed which in turn are helping to increase the speed of trains. Indian Railways aims to increase the speed of its passenger trains to 140–180 km/h on conventional tracks. Thus it can be seen from the trending aspects of railways that they are primarily focusing on increasing the speed rather than the SAFETY of the passengers. The primary focus should be the safety of passengers. Generally it is seen that when a train compartment catches fire due to any reason it's not easy to detect the fire initially and react to it. Due to which train does not stop instantly, which results in casualties and heavy damage to train. The objective of this paper is to design an Automatic Fire initiated braking and alert system for trains. This system consist a microcontroller, motor, fire and smoke sensor, alarm, and alert system. This paper proposes an embedded system that will be used to alert people so that life as well as the damage can be minimized. If the train coach catches fire, the smoke sensor will sense it and send a signal to the microcontroller. This microcontroller activates the motor to pull the chain and also activates an emergency alert system which sends an alert message to the train driver and guard room and activates the alarm. If the chain system to stop the train does not work properly, then even in that case, this system is very effective. So this system is useful to protect precious lives of passengers and minimize the heavy damages due to the fire accidents.

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM DESIGN

(3.1): L293D (MOTOR DRIVER IC):

A motor driver IC is an integrated circuit chip which is usually used to control motors in autonomous robots. Motor driver ICs act as an interface between microprocessors in robots and the motors in the robot. The most commonly used motor driver IC's are from the L293 series such as L293D, L293NE, etc. These ICs are designed to control 2 DC motors simultaneously. L293D consist of two H-bridge. H-bridge is the simplest circuit for controlling a low current rated motor. For this tutorial we will be referring the motor driver IC as L293D only. L293D has 16 pins.

Motor Driver ICs are primarily used in autonomous robotics only. Also most microprocessors operate at low voltages and require a small amount of current to operate while the motors require a relatively higher voltages and current . Thus current cannot be supplied to the motors from the microprocessor. This is the primary need for the motor driver IC.

The L293D IC receives signals from the microprocessor and transmits the relative signal to the motors. It has two voltage pins, one of which is used to draw current for the working of the L293D and the other is used to apply voltage to the motors. The L293D switches it output signal according to the input received from the microprocessor. For Example: If the microprocessor sends a 1(digital high) to the Input Pin of L293D, then the L293D transmits a 1(digital high) to the motor from its Output Pin. An important thing to note is that the L293D simply transmits the signal it receives. It does not change the signal in any case. The L293D is a 16 pin IC, with eight pins, on each side, dedicated to the controlling of a motor. There are 2 INPUT pins, 2 OUTPUT pins and 1 ENABLE pin for each motor. L293D consist of two H-bridge. H-bridge is the simplest circuit for controlling a low current rated motor.

Working Of A H-bridge

H-bridge is given this name because it can be modelled as four switches on the corners of 'H'. The basic diagram of H-bridge is given below :

Fig. (3.1): Figure of H-bridge.

In the given diagram, the arrow on the left points to the higher potential side of the input voltage of the circuit. Now if the switches **S1** & **S4** are kept in a **closed** position while the switches **S2** & **S3** are kept in a **open** position meaning that the circuit gets shorted across the switches **S1** & **S4**. This creates a path for the current to flow, starting from the **V** input to switch **S1** to the **motor**, then to switch **S4** and then the exiting from the circuit. This flow of the current would make the motor turn in one direction. The direction of motion of the motor can be clockwise or

anti-clockwise, this is because the rotation of the motor depends upon the connection of the terminals of the motor with the switches.

For simplicity, let's assume that in this condition the motor rotates in a clockwise direction. Now, when **S3** and **S2** are **closed** then and **S1** and **S4** are kept **open** then the current flows from the other direction and the motor will now definitely rotate in counter-clockwise direction. When **S1** and **S3** are closed and **S2** and **S4** are **open** then the 'STALL' condition will occur (The motor will break).

Now depending upon the values of the Input and Enable the motors will rotate in either clockwise or anticlockwise direction with full speed (when Enable is HIGH) or with less speed (when Enable is provided with PWM).

Let us assume for Left Motor when Enable is HIGH and Input 1 and Input 2 are HIGH and LOW respectively then the motor will move in clockwise direction.

So the behavior of the motor depending on the input conditions will be as follows :

input 1	input 2	enable 1,2	Result
0	0	1	Stop
0	1	1	Anti-clockwise rotation
1	0	1	Clockwise rotation
1	1	1	Stop
0	1	50% duty cycle	Anti-clockwise rotation with half speed
1	0	50% duty cycle	Clockwise rotation with half speed

(3.2): At-Mega 16 MICROCONTROLLER:

Features

1. High-performance, Low-power Atmel AVR,8-bit Microcontroller
2. Advanced RISC Architecture
 - 131 Powerful Instructions – Most
 - Single-clock Cycle Execution
 - 32 × 8 General Purpose Working Registers
 - Fully Static Operation
 - Up to 16 MIPS Throughput at 16 MHz
 - On-chip 2-cycle Multiplier
3. High Endurance Non-volatile Memory segments
 - 16 Kbytes of In-System Self-programmable Flash program memory
 - 512 Bytes EEPROM
 - 1 Kbyte Internal SRAM
 - Write/Erase Cycles: 10,000 Flash/100,000 EEPROM
 - Data retention: 20 years at 85°C/100 years at 25°C
 - Optional Boot Code Section with Independent Lock Bits In-System Programming by On-chip Boot Program
 - True Read-While-Write Operation
 - Programming Lock for Software Security

4. Peripheral Features

- Two 8-bit Timer/Counters with Separate Prescalers and Compare Modes
- One 16-bit Timer/Counter with Separate Prescaler, Compare Mode, and Capture Mode
- Real Time Counter with Separate Oscillator
- Four PWM Channels
- 8-channel, 10-bit ADC
 - 8 Single-ended Channels
 - 7 Differential Channels in TQFP Package Only
 - 2 Differential Channels with Programmable Gain at 1x, 10x, or 200x
- Byte-oriented Two-wire Serial Interface
- Programmable Serial USART
- Master/Slave SPI Serial Interface
- Programmable Watchdog Timer with Separate On-chip Oscillator
- On-chip Analog Comparator

5. Special Microcontroller Features

- Power-on Reset and Programmable Brown-out Detection
- Internal Calibrated RC Oscillator
- External and Internal Interrupt Sources
- Six Sleep Modes: Idle, ADC Noise Reduction, Power-save, Power-down, Standby and Extended Standby

6. I/O and Packages

- 32 Programmable I/O Lines
- 40-pin PDIP, 44-lead TQFP, and 44-pad QFN/MLF

The ATmega16 is a low-power CMOS 8-bit microcontroller based on the AVR enhanced RISC architecture. By executing powerful instructions in a single clock cycle, the ATmega16 achieves throughputs approaching 1 MIPS per MHz allowing the system designer to optimize power consumption versus processing speed

The AVR core combines a rich instruction set with 32 general purpose working registers. All the 32 registers are directly connected to the Arithmetic Logic Unit (ALU), allowing two independent registers to be accessed in one single instruction executed in one clock cycle. The resulting architecture is more code efficient while achieving throughputs up to ten times faster than conventional CISC microcontrollers.

The ATmega16 provides the following features: 16 Kbytes of In-System Programmable Flash Program memory with Read-While-Write capabilities, 512 bytes EEPROM, 1 Kbyte SRAM, 32 general purpose I/O lines, 32 general purpose working registers, a JTAG interface for Boundary-scan, On-chip Debugging support and programming, three flexible Timer/Counters with compare modes, Internal and External Interrupts, a serial programmable USART, a byte oriented two-wire Serial Interface, an 8-channel, 10-bit ADC with optional differential input stage with programmable gain (TQFP package only), a programmable Watchdog Timer with Internal Oscillator, an SPI serial port, and six software selectable power saving modes. The Idle mode stops the CPU while allowing the USART, Two-wire interface, A/D Converter, SRAM, Timer/Counters, SPI port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode

saves the register contents but freezes the Oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next External Interrupt or Hardware Reset. In Power-save mode, the Asynchronous Timer continues to run, allowing the user to maintain a timer base while the rest of the device is sleeping. The ADC Noise Reduction mode stops the CPU and all I/O modules except Asynchronous Timer and ADC, to minimize switching noise during ADC conversions. In Standby mode, the crystal/resonator Oscillator is running while the rest of the device is sleeping. This allows very fast start-up combined with low-power consumption. In Extended Standby mode, both the main Oscillator and the Asynchronous Timer continue to run. The device is manufactured using Atmel's high density nonvolatile memory technology. The On chip ISP Flash allows the program memory to be reprogrammed in-system through an SPI serial interface, by a conventional nonvolatile memory programmer, or by an On-chip Boot program running on the AVR core. The boot program can use any interface to download the application program in the Application Flash memory. Software in the Boot Flash section will continue to run while the Application Flash section is updated, providing true Read-While-Write operation. By combining an 8-bit RISC CPU with In-System Self-Programmable Flash on a monolithic chip, the Atmel ATmega16 is a powerful microcontroller that provides a highly-flexible and cost-effective solution to many embedded control applications. The ATmega16 AVR is supported with a full suite of program and system development tools including: C compilers, macro assemblers, program debugger/simulators, in-circuit emulators, and evaluation kits.

Fig. (3.2): Figure of Microcontroller Atmega-16.

(3.3): MOTOR (DC GEARED):

A geared DC Motor has a gear assembly attached to the motor. The speed of motor is counted in terms of rotations of the shaft per minute and is termed as RPM .The gear assembly helps in increasing the torque and reducing the speed. Using the correct combination of gears in a gear motor, its speed can be reduced to any desirable figure. This concept where gears reduce the speed of the vehicle but increase its torque is known as gear reduction. External Structure At the first sight, the external structure of a DC geared motor looks as a straight expansion over the simple DC ones.

The lateral view of the motor shows the outer protrudes of the gear head. A nut is placed near the shaft which helps in mounting the motor to the other parts of the assembly. Also, an internally threaded hole is there on the shaft to allow attachments or extensions such as wheel to be attached to the motor.

Fig. (3.3a, 3.3b): Outer Part of DC Geared Motor.

The outer body of the gear head is made of high density plastic but it is quite easy to open as only screws are used to attach the outer and the inner structure. The major reason behind this could be to lubricate gear head from time to time.

The plastic body has a threading through which nut can be easily mounted and vice versa from the gear head.

Internal Structure

On opening the outer plastic casing of the gear head, gear assemblies on the top as well as on bottom part of the gear head are visible. These gear assemblies are highly lubricated with grease so as to avoid any sort of wear and tear due to frictional forces. Shown below is the top part of the gear head. It is connected to rotating shaft and has one gear that allows the rotation. A strong circular imprint shows the presence of the gear that rotates the gear at the upper portion.

Fig. (3.4a, 3.4b): Internal Part of DC Geared Motor.

A closer look at the bottom gear assembly shows the structure and connection with other gears. Gear assembly's association with the motor (bottom gear assembly) can be understood with the help of the image shown below.

The gears are basically in form of a small sprocket but since they are not connected by a chain, they can be termed as duplex gears in terms of a second cog arrangement coaxially over the base. Among the three gears, two are exactly same while the third one is bigger in terms of the number of teeth at the upper layer of the duplex gear. The third gear is connected to the gear at the upper portion of the gear head. The manner in which they are located near the upper part of the gear head.

Working of the DC Geared Motor

The DC motor works over a fair range of voltage. The higher the input voltage more is the RPM (rotations per minute) of the motor. For example, if the motor works in the range of 6-12V, it will have the least RPM at 6V and maximum at 12 V.

In terms of voltage, we can put the equation as:

$RPM = K_1 * V$, where,

K_1 = induced voltage constant

V = voltage applied

The working of the gears is very interesting to know. It can be explained by the principle of conservation of angular momentum. The gear having smaller radius will cover more RPM than the one with larger radius. However, the larger gear will give more torque to the smaller gear than vice versa. The comparison of angular velocity between input gear (the one that transfers energy) to output gear gives the gear ratio. When multiple gears are connected together, conservation of energy is also followed. The direction in which the other gear rotates is always the opposite of the gear adjacent to it.

In any DC motor, RPM and torque are inversely proportional. Hence the gear having more torque will provide a lesser RPM and converse. In a geared DC motor, the concept of pulse width modulation is applied.

In a geared DC motor, the gear connecting the motor and the gear head is quite small, hence it transfers more speed to the larger teeth part of the gear head and makes it rotate. The larger part of the gear further turns the smaller duplex part. The small duplex part receives the torque but not the speed from its predecessor which it transfers to larger part of other gear and so on. The third gear's duplex part has more teeth than others and hence it transfers more torque to the gear that is connected to the shaft.

(3.4): RF RECEIVER AND TRANSMITTER:

The RF module, as the name suggests, operates at Radio Frequency. The corresponding frequency range varies between 30 kHz & 300 GHz. In this RF system, the digital data is represented as variations in the amplitude of carrier wave. This kind of modulation is known as Amplitude Shift Keying (ASK).

Transmission through RF is better than IR (infrared) because of many reasons. Firstly, signals through RF can travel through larger distances making it suitable for long range applications. Also, while IR mostly operates in line-of-sight mode, RF signals can travel even when there is an

obstruction between transmitter & receiver. Next, RF transmission is more strong and reliable than IR transmission. RF communication uses a specific frequency unlike IR signals which are affected by other IR emitting sources.

Fig. (3.5): RF Receiver and Transmitter.

This RF module comprises of an RF Transmitter and an RF Receiver. The transmitter/receiver (Tx/Rx) pair operates at a frequency of 434 MHz. An RF transmitter receives serial data and transmits it wirelessly through RF through its antenna connected at pin4. The transmission occurs at the rate of 1Kbps - 10Kbps. The transmitted data is received by an RF receiver operating at the same frequency as that of the transmitter.

CHAPTER FOUR

WORKING OF THE PROJECT

(4.1): WORKING OF SYSTEM:

We can divide the working of system in following steps:

Step 01: Fire will be initiated in train's compartment.

Step 02: Smoke of the fire will be immediately detected by the smoke sensors.

Step 03: Smoke sensor will send a signal to the microcontroller Atmega-16.

Step 04: Microcontroller At-mega 16 will:

1. Send a signal to L293D (motor controller IC) to start the motor for pulling the chain.
2. Send a signal to buzzer for alerting passengers.
3. Send a signal to another transmitter r.f. module (335 MHz).

Step 05: In this step all three works will be done together, the works are:

1. L293D (motor controller IC) will start the motor and chain of the train will be pulled.
2. The buzzer will start alerting people.
3. The train's driver will be informed and alerted about the fire as soon as possible by the buzzer and he will stop the train as soon as possible.

Resultant of this process will lower the pressure of the train's braking pipe and it will lead to the stopping of train within time to save the lives of innocent passengers.

Fig. (4.1): Block Diagram of the Braking System

Fig. (4.2): Wireless system inside the train's passenger coach

Fig. (4.3): Wireless system inside the train's

CHAPTER FIVE

IMPLEMENTATION AND LEGACY OF THE PROJECT

Fig. (5.1): Sensors and Transmitter in the wood board.

Fig. (5.2, 5.3): Burning of program in module through Burner.

(5.1): FAILURES OF THE PROJECT: The system is has many failures some parts of this failure are:

(5.1.a).USE OF CO AXIAL CABLE:

Coaxial cable is the kind of copper cable used by cable TV companies between the community antenna and user homes and businesses. Coaxial cable is called "coaxial" because it includes one

physical channel that carries the signal surrounded (after a layer of insulation) by another concentric physical channel, both running along the same axis. The outer channel serves as a ground. Many of these cables or pairs of coaxial tubes can be placed in a single outer sheathing and, with repeaters, can carry information for a great distance. Coaxial cable is sometimes used by telephone companies from their central office to the telephone poles near users.

The center layer is a thin conducting wire, either solid or braided copper. A dielectric layer, made up of an insulating material with very well-defined electrical characteristics, surrounds the wire. A shield layer then surrounds the dielectric layer with metal foil or braided copper mesh. The whole assembly is wrapped in an insulating jacket. A key to coaxial cable design is tight control of cable dimensions and materials. Together, they ensure that the characteristic impedance of the cable takes on a fixed value. High-frequency signals are partially reflected at impedance mismatches, causing errors.

Characteristic impedance is sensitive to signal frequency. Above 1 GHz, the cable maker must use a dielectric that doesn't attenuate the signal too much, or change the characteristic impedance in a way that creates signal reflections. Vendor specs should provide guidance.

Connectors for coax range from simple single connectors used on cable TV systems to complicated combinations of multiple thin coax links, mixed with power and other signal connections, housed in semi-custom bodies. These are commonly found in military electronics and avionics.

Mechanical stiffness can vary tremendously, depending on the internal construction and intended use of the coaxial cabling. For example, high-power cables are often made with thick insulation and are very stiff.

Some cables are deliberately made with thick center wires, resulting in skin-effect resistance. It results from high-frequency signals traveling on the surface of the conductor, not throughout. If the center conductor is larger, it results in a stiff cable with low loss per meter.

Fig. (5.4): Internal parts of Co-Axial Cable.

(5.1.b): USE OF RUBBER DUCK ANTENNA (GHz):

The **rubber ducky antenna** (or rubber duck aerial) is an electrically monopole antenna that functions somewhat like a base-loaded whip antenna. It consists of a springy wire in the shape of a narrow helix, sealed in a rubber or plastic jacket to protect the antenna.

Electrically short antennas like the rubber ducky are used in portable handheld radio equipment at VHF and UHF frequencies in place of a quarter wavelength whip antenna, which is inconveniently long and cumbersome at these frequencies. Many years after its invention in 1958, the rubber ducky antenna became the antenna of choice for many portable radio devices, including transceivers and scanners and other devices where safety and robustness take precedence over antenna capabilities.

Fig. (5.5): Internal parts of Co-Axial Cable.

CHAPTER SIX

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